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**INTERACTIVE DEVELOPING OF ORAL SPEECH COMPETENCE IN
TEACHING ENGLISH FOR THE MILITARY LAWYERS THROUGH
AUTHOR'S INNOVATIVE "DIGITAL CASE STUDY" VIDEO LESSONS**

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Abstract: The following research work focuses on the process of developing oral speech competence of English for the military lawyers. It is aimed to analyze the existing obstacles and barriers which are preventing the learners from foreign oral communication and to find the appropriate solutions to these problems. There has been an attempt to create more suitable teaching strategies for the Higher Military Educational Institutions. We propose renewed and a complex set of teaching strategies involving special interactive activities and using innovative technologies in EFL classes.

Keywords: The author's new method- Digital Case-study, the pluses of digital methods, reflection for deep learning, technology integration, Start-up lesson, new aspect- watching and analyzing, oral speech, Higher Military Educational Institutions, cadets, speech situations, interaction patterns, interactive teaching strategies.

Introduction: We organized different surveys using questionnaires, open discussions with the cadets; provided research-analyses, author's digital case-studies and observations with foreign language teachers in order to investigate the problems in this area and held experiment lessons, out-of-class trainings considering the learners' needs, their preferences in organizing the foreign lessons, their week-points and other crucial features described below in this article. The results and conclusions are presented at the end of the work. The research considers the author's methods and means of developing oral speech competence in teaching English for military lawyers and taking into account the advantages and disadvantages of these tools equally, thus, trying to determine the most effective and suitable ones among them. It considers some specific interaction patterns, communicative activities, and other educational methods and tools as major components of successful teaching both in educational and psychological aspects. Our book "Interactive English for Military Lawyers by Murakayeva Sh." and author's methods "Digital case-study" and "Start-up lesson": English language training for cadets in higher military educational institutions prepared for the doctoral degree in pedagogy on the topic of theory and methodology of education and upbringing. Proposals and methodological recommendations on the practical application of the improvement of the interactive information-methodological support of the development of oral speech competence and on the improvement of the skills of acquiring the English language the proposed methodological system was introduced into the Higher Military Educational Institutions as a result of methodological developments, the "Digital Case" and "Startup Lesson" serve as a scientific

and methodological resource. Digital case-study on the basis of digital storytelling can be defined as the process by which cadets share their professional cases and experiences with others. A newer form of storytelling our Digital Case study is emerging with the advent of affordable media techniques, hardware and software, including but not limited to digital cameras, digital voice recorders, iMovie, Microsoft Photos, Final Cut Express, and WeVideo. These new technologies allow cadets to share their professional experiences online on YouTube, Video, CDs, podcasts and other electronic distribution systems. Instead of ordinary reading- you will listen and watch professional cases as real. Digital Storytelling was first used in 1990 by Ken Burns in his documentary epic film Civil War Ken Burns Digital Storytelling (American Civil War 1861-1865). It was Digital srorytelling, not Digital Professional Case Study as we have.

The first hyper llesson with digital storytelling was conducted by teacher on history about the American Civil War. It was first applied in the educational process at Harvard Law School in 1870, but the introduction of this method at Harvard Business School began in 1920. The first collections of cases were published in 1925 in the Harvard University Business Reports. Currently, 2 classical schools of case-study coexist - Harvard (American) and Manchester (European). State University of New York: Clyde Freeman Harried successfully used the case study in a classroom for teaching the natural sciences. In 1994, the National Center of the Case Study for different sciences was established in the United States in order to promote case studies reforming science teaching at all. In the field of education, the term "case" got into the beginning of 20th century In 1910: the dean of the Harvard Business School (USA), Christopher Columbus Langdell (we are not talking about seafarer/voyager), advised teachers to introduce into the educational process, in addition to traditional classes - lectures and workshops - discussions with cadets. Cadets were offered a description of a specific practical situations from the practice of their future activities that needed to be solved, i.e. the training was conducted according to the principle "from typical situational examples to the rules. Langdell set himself the task of organizing the academic preparation of cadets closer to the field of their future professional activity and replaced traditional lectures with a discussion of real cases from legal practice. The professor offered cadets to prepare in advance for the lesson by examining large folders with documents. This experience was recognized at the faculty as promising and was subsequently used by some other teachers. So what about our method: There have never been digital case study before, only reading passages as

situation 1, 2, 3 in American military books as Campaign English for the military.

We have created the Digital Case Study, that is video-cases within the framework of Digital Storytelling. As we know by 1915 the case study was used in the educational process in some US law schools. By 1920, a number of Langdell's followers were using the case method in teaching not only law but also medicine and business administration. However, the case method remaining unknown to a wide range of specialists.

It is not about just reading passages like in Campaign books: situation 1, situation 2, situation 3:

Situation 1.

1. A small group of individuals are following your patrol

2. The platoon receives sniper fire from a second storey window. No one is hurt.

3. There is a car one metre ahead of you, blocking the road. You suspect an ambush.

Instead of reading these highly professional cases you will watch it: pictures, infographics and photos with your voice. **Prioritized learning based on different disciplines on the base of new author's method Digital Case-study:**

teaching, through language skills, through process teaching, complex teaching, content, interdisciplinary, episodic, partial, analytical, quasi (pseudo) teaching coexist and work effectively in learning and the difference between them is in the priority distribution or in the sequence of four and each of them is represented in the aspect priority scheme. Everything is very clear and simple.

Language training of military higher education institutions

1. Horizontal education of competence-based learning

2. Vertical integration of competence-based learning

3. Systemic-integration competency training

4. Through language skills

6. Content learning

7. Process-integrated learning is associated in a priority way with speaking, that is, with oral speech in the first place: All aspects and, therefore, tasks come from and are based on speaking, since even cognitive perception requires an internal foreign monologue, and monologues and dialogues, in turn, are related to speech activity.

8. Quasi education which consists of 3 aspects:

Throughout the history of science, the theory and practice of developing oral speech competence and speech competence have been studied by such scientists: Teachers of Uzbekistan M. Gulyamova, B. Samatova, A. Rakhmonov, J. Abduganieva, B. Muradkosimova, Sh. Akbarova, L. Shosaidova Locke, I. Gebart, M. Pestalozzi, K. Ushinsky, specialists in didactics A. Danilov, V. Maksimova, I. Zverev and, importantly, psychologists paid special attention to the development of oral speech such as N. Talizina, Yu. Samarina, G. Vergels, as well as specialists in teaching methods G. Pristupova, M. Lvov, G. Goretsky. On the basis of oral speech competence and a speech approach to the study of foreign languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the leading scientific methodologists D. Sokolova, N. Sattorova, J. Yalolov, I. Kazakbaeva, D. Olimova, M. Beryadeva, D. Kurbanbaev, G. Makhkamova, H. Mamatkulov, K. Riskulova. The concepts of competence and competence first appeared in linguistics in the middle of the 20th century in 1955. N. Chomsky interprets these concepts as: "A set of activity-oriented knowledge and skills in the process of using the language", while the competence-based approach as a whole is mentioned as a factor indicating performance in education.

In Uzbekistan, this concept of competence-based learning began to be introduced into the education system from the 90s: J. Yalolov considered competence-based learning as learning the abilities of a certain profession, while N. Sattorov considered competence-based learning, as well as teaching mastery in pedagogy in the form of a qualification of a future specialist. This term is also interpreted differently in different dictionaries of our Republic.

We will consider some of them: in the second volume of the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the following definition is given notion "competence" (from Latin Competere) - to be worthy of a title or profession

A. The scope of authority of a specific body or official, established by official public or private documents, that is, a person's awareness of a particular area and the degree of

his or her knowledge of the specialty of education

B. In the dictionary reference book of higher education, in turn: competence is applicability as a term of reference, rights and obligations of a particular public institution;

C. Range of issues on which a particular official acquires knowledge, experience;

D. Competence (lat. competence-relevance) - is the degree of knowledge to solve problems of a certain level of complexity and issues in the specialty.

Unlike the term "qualification", that is, in addition to including pure professional knowledge and abilities that characterize qualifications, it also includes such qualities as "initiative", "cooperation", "ability" to work in a group, that is, the presence of a communicative and proper oral speech competence is by no means excluded, but is put one of the first - super priority. Learning, evaluative learning, logical thinking, the ability to choose and use information are the main components of competence-based learning. According to the definitions given in the words "competence". Different points of view, the relations expressed in them are reflected in the table below:

Definitions and difference between interpretations of the "competence" in the works of different scientists:

№	Researchers	Definitions of researchers
1.	M. Gulyamova	Competence - the degree of compatibility of knowledge, skills and experience of persons with a certain social professional position with the level of complexity of the tasks they perform and the operations they solve.
2.	J. Jalolov	Competence is an attempt to learn a language as the ability to master it.
3.	E. Azimov	Competence is a combination of skills and abilities formed in the process of learning one of the disciplines
4.	G. Asilova	Competence is a set of personal acquired qualities, as well as knowledge and skills in the process of activity in a certain area
5.	K. Riskulova	Competence is the rapid design of solutions in the course of incoming tasks and the acquired creativity in the process of solving problems.

The problem of the development of oral speech of pupils at the senior stage of general educational school is becoming increasingly important since speech as the purpose of learning acts as a means of communication. Today, the aim of a modern school is to form a multicultural personality of pupils, which implies that they acquire a certain amount of knowledge about a foreign language, the formation of the ability not only to understand but also to communicate freely in it. As noted by O. A. Biryukova and D. V. Semenova, "the formation of the ability to produce one's own oral speech in monologue and dialogical forms in modern methodological science is postulated as the main goal of teaching a foreign language and is expressed through the concept of foreign language communicative competence, which, as is known, has a rather complex multicomponent structure". Oral speech as a productive process requires a lot of time and effort from the student since it also requires the inclusion of language, speech and communicative competencies. As a type of communicative activity, it should be an integral part of every lesson. "The main purpose of teaching a foreign language to pupils is the possession of basic speech structures that correspond to the threshold level of proficiency based on the All-European Scale of Language Competence. Teaching speaking is based on themes that meet the real needs and interests of pupils at the senior stage of general educational school." S. B. Suvorova offers her own classification of interactive teaching methods based on communicative functions. In this classification, all methods are divided into three groups: 1) discussion (dialogue, group discussion, analysis and analysis of life situations); 2) gaming (didactic games, business games, roleplaying games, organizational and activity methods); 3) psychological group of interactive methods (sensitive and communicative training, empathy)

Conclusion

So we conclude that the interactive lesson is an impromptu training session that has an unconventional structure. It is easy to notice that some types of classes were included in the category of interactive lessons, which in the previous classifications appeared as auxiliary, extra-curricular, and extracurricular forms of organization of educational work, and their names give some idea of the goals, objectives, and methods of conducting such classes. It must be concluded that cadets in the interactive lessons are diligent and diligent. They don't have to get bored. And finally, the marks that the cadets receive for the lesson are much higher than those they receive in traditional lessons. Interactive teaching methods are a special form of organizing cognitive and communicative activities in which cadets find themselves involved in the cognitive process, have the ability to understand and reflect on what they know and think. Teacher's place in interactive lessons often comes down to directing cadets to achieve lesson goals. He develops a lesson plan (as a rule, this is a set of interactive exercises and assignments, during which the student learns the material). Thus, the main components of interactive lessons are interactive exercises and assignments that are performed by cadets. The fundamental difference between interactive exercises and tasks from ordinary ones is that in the course of their implementation not only material already

learned is fixed, but also new material is studied. Interactive exercises and assignments are designed for so-called interactive approaches

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